

Interview Guides

Version 1

September 23 2024

“Thank you for agreeing to this interview about your experiences as an immigrant software engineer. As a reminder, your participation is voluntary, you don’t have to answer any question you don’t want to answer, and you can withdraw at any time by simply disconnecting the call. Is it ok if I start the recording?”.

[START RECORDING AND TRANSCRIPTION.]

Introductory Questions (Questions about participants background for initial context)

1. To begin, could you please introduce yourself and tell me a bit about your background and current role?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

- a. What country do you work in?
- b. How long have you been in your current role?
- c. How long have you been living and working in this country?
- d. Did you have any other jobs in your current country before this one?
- e. What are your main responsibilities at this organization?

Immigration Journey and Experience

2. What motivated you to move to your current country?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. What were your main reasons for immigrating?
- b. How that process was for you
- c. How did you find the immigration process? Were there any challenges?
- d. Did you get any support from your organization during the immigration process?
- e. What is your country of origin?
- f. What were your expectations before moving, compared with the reality?

3. Did you immigrate alone or with family?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. How was it like moving with your family?

- b. Were there any specific challenges while relocating your family?
[IF No]
 - c. Did you have to leave family members in your home country?
 - d. How does being away from your family affect you?
 - e. Do you support family back home, such as sending money or staying connected in other ways?
4. How has your adjustment to life in your current country been so far?
- Possible Follow Ups/Probes:
- a. What were some of the biggest challenges you faced when you first arrived?
 - b. Have you experienced any cultural differences that were surprising or difficult to navigate?
 - c. How have you navigated cultural differences outside your organization?
5. Has your immigration status influenced your career and professional opportunities here? If so, how?
- Possible Follow Ups/Probes:
- a. Do you feel your immigration status has affected your job choices or advancement opportunities?
 - b. Have you encountered any barriers in your professional life due to being an immigrant?
 - c. What is your current immigration status and how secure do you feel in it?
 - d. Does your organization treat you differently from citizens? If so, how?
 - e. What has been your experience adjusting within your organization?
6. Have you been able to establish connections within your geographical area?
- Possible Follow Ups/Probes:
- a. How have these connections influenced your sense of belonging?
 - b. Are you part of any clubs, associations, or religious groups?
 - c. Do you have anything that is keeping you rooted here, such as purchasing a home or marriage?
7. How has your immigration experience influenced your personal life here?

Intentions to Leave

8. Have you considered leaving your current job?
- Possible Follow Ups/Probes:
- a. Can you share what prompted these thoughts?
 - b. Are you looking for a new job right now?
 - c. Would you look for a new job in the same country?

- d. How likely are you to move to a new country?
9. What are your thoughts about your future in your current country and with your current employer?
- a. Do you see yourself staying here long-term?
 - b. Have you considered moving back to your home country or relocating elsewhere?
 - c. What factors are most important to you when making these decisions?
10. What don't you like about your job?
- a. If you decided to look for a new job, what would you look for?
11. What factors influence your decision to stay at or leave your current job?
- a. How significant are these factors in your decision-making process?
 - b. How does your immigration status play into this decision?
12. Do you feel tied to your current employer due to your immigration status?
- a. Would changing jobs affect your visa or residency status?
 - b. How does this influence your willingness to seek new opportunities?
13. What would you lose if you changed jobs?
- Possible Follow Ups/Probes
- a. How significant are these losses to you?
 - b. What would you move to a different location but the same country?
 - c. What would you move to another country?

Job Satisfaction (questions about how people feel about what they do at work)

14. What do you like about your job?
- Possible Probes
- a. Team mates, team dynamics, management, culture, projects, tooling, language, office space, organization, benefits, salary, policies (e.g. can work from home).
 - b. How does X work?
 - c. Why do you like it?

15. What don't you like about your job?
 - a. Team mates, team dynamics, management, culture, projects, tooling, language, office space, organization, benefits, salary, policies (e.g. can work from home).
 - b. How does X work?
 - c. What's wrong with it?
 - d.
 - e. If you decided to look for a new job, what would you look for?
 - i. Are you looking for a job in a different country or this country?
 - ii. Are you looking for a company with immigration support?

16. How do you feel about your work and the tasks you perform?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. What aspects are most satisfying or challenging?
17. What technologies and tools do you use in your role?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. How do you feel about these tools in terms of productivity and efficiency?
18. How is work typically organized in your team? Can you describe how meetings, project planning, and teamwork are structured?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. How do you feel about these work structures you just talked about?
19. Can you tell me about your team?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. How do you find the dynamics and interaction within your team?
 - b. Are you friends with your colleagues at work?
20. What opportunities for learning and development are available to you in your current role?
 - a. How easily accessible are these opportunities?
21. Can you describe the core values that guide you in your professional life?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. How would you describe the core values of your company?
 - b. Now, which of your personal values align with those of the company?**

Version 2

Jan 31, 2025

“Thank you for agreeing to this interview about your experiences as an immigrant software engineer. As a reminder, your participation is voluntary, you don't have to answer any question you don't want to answer, and you can withdraw at any time by simply disconnecting the call. Is it ok if I start the recording?”.

[START RECORDING AND TRANSCRIPTION.]

Introductory Questions (Questions about participants background for initial context)

1. To begin, could you please introduce yourself and tell me a bit about your background and current role?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

- a. What country do you work in?
- b. How long have you been in your current role?
- c. How long have you been living and working in this country?
- d. Did you have any other jobs in your current country before this one?
- e. What are your main responsibilities at this organization?

Immigration Journey and Experience

2. What motivated you to move to your current country?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. What were your main reasons for immigrating?
- b. How that process was for you
- c. How did you find the immigration process? Were there any challenges?
- d. Did you get any support from your organization during the immigration process?
- e. What were your expectations before moving, compared with the reality?
- f. Do you think of going back home?
- g. How often do you go back home?
- h. What is your country of origin?

3. Did you immigrate alone or with family?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. How was it like moving with your family?
- b. Were there any specific challenges while relocating your family?
[IF No]
- c. Did you have to leave family members in your home country?
- d. How does being away from your family affect you?
- e. Do you support family back home, such as sending money or staying connected in other ways?

4. How has your adjustment to life in your current country been so far?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. What were some of the biggest challenges you faced when you first arrived?
 - b. Have you experienced any cultural differences that were surprising or difficult to navigate?
 - c. How have you navigated cultural differences outside your organization?
5. Has your immigration status influenced your career and professional opportunities here? If so, how?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. Do you feel your immigration status has affected your job choices or advancement opportunities?
 - b. Have you encountered any barriers in your professional life due to being an immigrant?
 - c. What is your current immigration status and how secure do you feel in it?
 - d. Does your organization treat you differently from citizens? If so, how?
 - e. What has been your experience adjusting within your organization?
6. Have you been able to establish connections within your geographical area?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. How have these connections influenced your sense of belonging?
 - b. Are you part of any clubs, associations, or religious groups?
 - c. Do you have anything that is keeping you rooted here, such as purchasing a home or marriage?
- 7. How has your immigration experience influenced your personal life here?**

Intentions to Leave

8. Have you considered leaving your current job?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. Can you share what prompted these thoughts?
 - b. Are you looking for a new job right now?
 - c. Would you look for a new job in the same country?
 - d. How likely are you to move to a new country?
9. What are your thoughts about your future in your current country and with your current employer?
- a. Do you see yourself staying here long-term?
 - b. Have you considered moving back to your home country or relocating elsewhere?
 - c. What factors are most important to you when making these decisions?

10. What factors influence your decision to stay at or leave your current job?
 - a. How significant are these factors in your decision-making process?
 - b. How does your immigration status play into this decision?

11. Do you feel tied to your current employer due to your immigration status?
 - a. Would changing jobs affect your visa or residency status?
 - b. How does this influence your willingness to seek new opportunities?

12. What would you lose if you changed jobs?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. How significant are these losses to you?
 - b. What would you move to a different location but the same country?
 - c. What would you move to another country?

Job Satisfaction (questions about how people feel about what they do at work)

13. What do you like about your job?

Possible Probes

 - a. Team mates, team dynamics, management, **culture**, projects, **tooling**, language, office space, organization, benefits, salary, policies (e.g. can work from home).
 - b. How does X work?
 - c. Why do you like it?

14. What don't you like about your job?
 - a. Team mates, team dynamics, management, culture, projects, tooling, language, office space, organization, benefits, salary, policies (e.g. can work from home).
 - b. How does X work?
 - c. What's wrong with it?
 - d.
 - e. If you decided to look for a new job, what would you look for?
 - i. Are you looking for a job in a different country or this country?
 - ii. Are you looking for a company with immigration support?

15. How do you feel about your work and the tasks you perform?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

 - a. What aspects are most satisfying or challenging?

16. What technologies and tools do you use in your role?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

a. How do you feel about these tools in terms of productivity and efficiency?

17. How is work typically organized in your team? Can you describe how meetings, project planning, and teamwork are structured?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

a. How do you feel about these work structures you just talked about?

18. Can you tell me about your team?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

a. How do you find the dynamics and interaction within your team?

b. Are you friends with your colleagues at work?

19. What opportunities for learning and development are available to you in your current role?

a. How easily accessible are these opportunities?

20. Do you feel your skills are valued to the fullest extent?

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21. Can you describe the core values that guide you in your professional life?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes

a. How would you describe the core values of your company?

b. Now, **which of your personal values align with those of the company?**

22. What prompted you to leave your home country?

a. **Do you think of going back home?**

b. **How often do you go back home?**

23. Do you contribute to the business beyond your technical skills

24. What does your company do that appeals most to your personal values

Version 3

March 13, 2025

“Thank you for agreeing to this interview about your experiences as an immigrant software engineer. As a reminder, your participation is voluntary, you don’t have to answer any question you don’t want to answer, and you can withdraw at any time by simply disconnecting the call. Is it ok if I start the recording?”.

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Possible Follow Ups/Probes

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- e. What are your main responsibilities at this organization?

Immigration Journey and Experience

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Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

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- e. What were your expectations before moving, compared with the reality?
- f. Do you think of going back home?
- g. How often do you go back home?
- h. What is your country of origin?

3. Did you immigrate alone or with family?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

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- b. Were there any specific challenges while relocating your family?
[IF No]
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- e. Do you support family back home, such as sending money or staying connected in other ways?

4. How has your adjustment to life in your current country been so far?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

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5. Has your immigration status influenced your career and professional opportunities here? If so, how?

Possible Follow Ups/Probes:

- a. Do you feel your immigration status has affected your job choices or advancement opportunities?
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- a. How significant are these factors in your decision-making process?
 - b. How does your immigration status play into this decision?
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- a. Would changing jobs affect your visa or residency status?
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Possible Follow Ups/Probes

- a. How significant are these losses to you?
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- b. How does X work?
- c. Why do you like it?

If they talk about remote work

- d. Why does remote work really matter to you?

14. What don't you like about your job?

- a. Team mates, team dynamics, management, culture, projects, tooling, language, office space, organization, benefits, salary, policies (e.g. can work from home).
- b. How does X work?
- c. What's wrong with it?

d.

- e. If you decided to look for a new job, what would you look for?
 - i. Are you looking for a job in a different country or this country?
 - ii. Are you looking for a company with immigration support

If they talk about remote work

- f. Why does remote work really matter to you?

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Possible Follow Ups/Probes
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- a. How do you find the dynamics and interaction within your team?
 - b. Are you friends with your colleagues at work?
19. What opportunities for learning and development are available to you in your current role?
- a. How easily accessible are these opportunities?
 - b. How useful are these opportunities to you? (Rev4)
- 20. Do you feel your skills are valued to the fullest extent?**
-
21. Can you describe the core values that guide you in your professional life?
Possible Follow Ups/Probes
- a. How would you describe the core values of your company?
 - b. Now, **which of your personal values align with those of the company?**
- 22. What prompted you to leave your home country?**
- a. **Do you think of going back home?**
 - b. **How often do you go back home?**
23. **Do you contribute to the business beyond your technical skills** (Rev2)
- 24. What does your company do that appeals most to your core values**

Demographic Survey

2. Demographic Survey

Now that you've passed our initial screening, we would like to collect some demographic information. Please answer the following questions to the best of your ability. Your responses will remain

confidential."

Demographic Questions

1. Where do you consider your home country?
2. What is your highest level of education? (Dropdown: High School, Bachelor's, Master's, PhD, Other)
3. Which country is your current work location?
4. What is your company's name and in which sector does it operate? (e.g., finance, tech, healthcare)
5. How long have you been working in your current country? (Number Field)
6. How many years of experience do you have in software engineering? (Number Field)
7. How long have you been with your current employer? (Number Field)
8. What is your marital status? (Dropdown: Single, Married, Divorced, Widowed, Other)
9. What is your annual income level? (Dropdown options based on the local currency and income brackets)
10. What is your age? (Number Field)
11. What is your gender? (Dropdown: Man, Woman, Non-binary, Prefer not to say, Prefer to self-describe [Text box])
12. To facilitate the scheduling of our interview, please chose your time zone and availability. (Date-Time Picker).
13. Did you receive your highest level of education in the country where you are currently working? (Yes/No).